

Photoassisted Solid-catalysed Reduction of N_2 by Water. Evidence for a Photostationary State and for Catalytic Activity of many Oxides[†]

NORMAN N. LICHTIN and KALAMBELLA M. VIJAYAKUMAR

Department of Chemistry, Boston University, Boston, Ma. 02215, U. S. A

Yields of NH_3 , produced when N_2 was contacted with bulk liquid water or water vapour over a number of metal oxides under illumination from xenon lamps, were measured under a range of conditions. Active catalysts included CoO , Co_3O_4 , $Co-Mo-Al$ -oxide, $Co-Mo-Ti$ -oxide, Cr_2O_3 , $\alpha-Fe_2O_3$, MoO_3 , Nd_2O_3 , PbO , Pr_2O_3 , TeO_2 , WO_3 , $Zn-Fe$ -oxide, $La-Ni$ -oxide and $La-Ti$ -oxide as well as a ferric ion-containing zeolite. System variables included period of reaction, short wavelength limit of light, temperature, flow-rate of gaseous reactant, weight of catalyst per unit volume of liquid water and concentration of initially added NH_3 . It has been shown that at or below 30° in the presence of illuminated suspensions of $\alpha-Fe_2O_3$ or Cr_2O_3 in water, NH_3 is both formed and decayed in the reaction cell so that a photostationary state is ultimately reached. A 40° or above, NH_3 can be swept out of the cell rapidly so that decay is negligible. Under the latter conditions, over $\alpha-Fe_2O_3$, $E_{activation} = 46 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. $E_{activation} = 19 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ over $\alpha-Fe_2O_3$ in the absence of bulk water. In the presence of either water vapor or liquid water, both $\alpha-Fe_2O_3$ and Cr_2O_3 maintained their catalytic activity for prolonged periods of time. The use of air did not alter the activity of Cr_2O_3 significantly. Several oxides with band-gap energies significantly smaller in magnitude than $E^\circ = 1.23 \text{ V}$ of the six-electron reduction of N_2 by H_2O to aqueous NH_4OH , are active catalysts. At least one step of the reaction must in these cases involve absorption of more than one photon per electron transferred.

THE sunlight-driven reduction of N_2 to ammonia by water is a potential route to fixation of nitrogen, the attractiveness of which lies in both avoidance of the high energy requirement of the Haber-Bosch process and in the possibility of generating ammonia at the locations of its use as an agricultural fertiliser. This paper reports results of an investigation of the photoassisted solid-catalysed reduction of N_2 by water and draws attention to some of the factors which affect efficiency of the process.

Photoassisted solid-catalysed reduction of N_2 by water was early described by Schrauzer and Guth¹. Their report describes experiments involving illumination of semiconductors in the presence of gases with no bulk liquid phase present. Most of these experiments employed pure or iron-doped powdered TiO_2 which had been heated in air to 1000° and then conditioned by exposure to the vapour pressure of water at room temperature. Illumination was usually with a 360 W mercury arc lamp through glass. Photodecomposition of water to H_2 and O_2 was observed when illumination took place under an argon atmosphere. Replacement of argon by N_2 inhibited production of H_2 completely and replaced it with NH_3 and 2-20 mol% of N_2H_4 . Replacement of half the N_2 by H_2 or Ar gave the same results, indicating that the reduction of N_2 by water does not involve H_2 as a reactant. NH_3 was also photo-

generated, although less efficiently, when air replaced pure N_2 . Anatase was less active catalytically than rutile. Doping TiO_2 with Fe increased catalytic activity, as did doping with Co, Mo and Ni, but incorporation of a number of other metals (Pd, Pt, Ag, Au, V, Cr, Pb and Cu) did not increase activity. $\alpha-Fe_2O_3$ catalysed formation of NH_3 from N_2 and H_2O but was less active than TiO_2 . N_2 also inhibited the photoreduction of acetylene over water-equilibrated TiO_2 or iron-doped TiO_2 with concomitant production of NH_3 . Neither quantum yields nor efficiencies of conversion of incident energies were measured. Related studies on photo-assisted catalysis of reduction of N_2 over various naturally-occurring sands were subsequently reported by Schrauzer and coworkers^{2,3}. Reduction of N_2 to NH_3 upon bubbling N_2 through aqueous suspensions of powdered semiconductors under illumination through borosilicate glass with a high-pressure mercury lamp was studied by Miyama and coworkers⁴. They found that yields of NH_3 obtained under standard conditions with TiO_2 , ZnO , $SrTiO_3$, CdS and GaP varied over a factor of about three, decreasing with increasing band-gap. The authors ascribed this trend to variation in the amount of light absorbed.

Somewhat larger-scale reduction of N_2 to NH_3 over a catalyst of Fe^{III} -doped TiO_2 supported on $\gamma-Al_2O_3$ under near-uv illumination with a

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

high-pressure mercury vapor lamp was studied by Augugliaro and coworkers⁵⁻⁸. These workers employed a fluidised bed reactor at 80-120° with a feedstock consisting of N₂ and water vapour. They calculated that the observed yields of NH₃ corresponded to consumption of 0.8-1.6 layers of surface hydroxyl per hour and found no diminution in hourly yields for more than 24 h. This result provides a significant answer for their conditions to the doubts expressed by Van Damme and Hall⁹ that the reactions observed by Schrauzer and Guth¹ were catalytic. Substantial increases in the photoefficiency of photoassisted reduction of N₂ by water by surface-loading of the rutile form of TiO₂ with iron clusters deposited by thermal decomposition of (C₆H₅)₂Fe(CH₃)₂ were reported by Radford and Francis¹⁰. Photoassisted reduction of N₂ to ammonia in suspensions of powdered TiO₂ in aqueous 1 M Na₂CO₃ has also been reported¹¹. Photoassisted reduction of N₂ by a suspension in water of a zeolite which had been exchanged with Ti^{III} has also been reported^{12,13}. However, this reaction apparently involves stoichiometric oxidation of Ti^{III} rather than oxidation of water.

Some of the results of our research on photoassisted solid-catalysed reduction by water of N₂ and mixtures of N₂ and CO₂ has been reported in the patent literature¹⁴⁻¹⁶ and in abstracts of papers^{17,18}.

Experimental

Two sets of conditions were employed, experiments in which reactant gases were bubbled through illuminated suspensions of catalyst powders in bulk liquid water and experiments in which N₂ and water vapour were passed in the absence of bulk liquid water over illuminated thin films of finely-divided catalyst powders deposited on an interior face of the cell. Reactants included N₂ alone and air. Light sources were 150 W Osram xenon lamps. The cell was located 30 cm from the lamp. The collimated beam illuminated 11 cm² of the approximately 25 cm² area of solution or film which was normal to the beam. Unless otherwise indicated, conditions of illumination were maintained constant within each set of data. Illumination cells were of Pyrex so that only light at λ > 300 nm was incident on the reactants. In many experiments, cut-off filters were used to exclude part or all of the ultraviolet. Reaction temperatures were controlled to ± 1°. Integrating devices based on the electrical output of silicon solar cells ('Sunstations'¹⁹) were used to monitor incident light energy. Catalyst powders (finer than 200 mesh, ASTM) were typically conditioned for use by heating at 100-400° under 1 atm of flowing argon for 24 h. NH₃ was determined colorimetrically by Nessler's method. Linde PP grade N₂ was routinely used. Reactant air was supplied by Linde. Flow-rates of reactant gases were 50-100 cm³min⁻¹ unless otherwise indicated.

Films of catalyst for use in the absence of bulk water were prepared by dispersing catalyst powder

in water or organic liquid and allowing the liquid to evaporate slowly while the powder deposited on the glass. Fresh films were dried in static air at 60-200° for 24 h and were then purged with flowing dry N₂ at 30° for 12 h before first use. Used films were similarly purged for 4-6 h between runs. Reactant N₂ was saturated with water vapor by bubbling it through liquid water. Figs. 1 and 2 are schematic diagrams of the apparatuses used, respectively, for

Fig. 1. Schematic of apparatus for reaction in presence of bulk liquid water: (1) light source: 150 W-Xe with quartz lenses, (2) glass filter, (3) blower, (4) gas cylinder, (5) needle valves, (6) flow meter, (7) chromous perchlorate deoxygenator, (8) water vapour saturator, (9) photochemical reactor, (10) magnetic stirrer, (11) condenser, (12) ice-cooled trap, (13) ice-cooled trap and (14) flow meter.

Fig. 2. Schematic of apparatus for reaction in absence of bulk liquid water: (1) gas cylinder, (2) valves, (3) flow meter, (4) chromous perchlorate deoxygenator, (5) water vapour saturator, (6) fritted glass vapor condenser, (7) thermostat, (8) blower, (9) flow meter, (10) light source: 150 W-Xe, (11) glass filter, (12) gas lines, (13) water bath, (14) magnetic stirrer, (15) reaction cell, (16) thermometer, (17) heat exchanger coils, (18) ice-cooled trap and (19) ice-cooled trap.

experiments in the presence and absence of bulk liquid water.

Results and Discussion

Reduction of N₂ in the presence of bulk liquid water: Ammonia was the only product observed in significant amounts when N₂ saturated with water vapor was bubbled through an illuminated dilute aqueous suspension of catalyst. At 30° or below, essentially all of this product remained in the reaction cell under reaction conditions. At 40° or above, most of the NH₃ was swept into the traps.

Tables 1 and 2 present data which indicate that with either α-Fe₂O₃ or Cr₂O₃ as catalyst, yields of ammonia approach limiting values. Each yield recorded in Table 1 was measured in a separate experiment, *i.e.* ammonia was only determined at the end of each experiment. A brief induction period is apparent in these data. With a constant proportion of catalyst, the yield of NH₃ then approaches a limiting value. The rate of approach to the plateau increases with the proportion of catalyst. Table 2 summarises data with Cr₂O₃ as a photocatalyst collected in the same way as the data of Table 1. Again, an approach to a limiting yield of NH₃ is apparent. Yields with air are essentially the same as with high-purity nitrogen. The limiting yield with Cr₂O₃ is approximately twice that observed with α-Fe₂O₃.

TABLE 1—REDUCTION OF N₂ OVER α-Fe₂O₃^a AT 28° UNDER ILLUMINATION^b AT λ ≥ 350 nm IN PRESENCE OF BULK LIQUID WATER. EVIDENCE FOR LIMITING YIELDS OF NH₃.

Proportion of catalyst w/v%	Reaction time h	Total yield of NH ₃ mol
0.10	0.17	Trace
0.10	0.33	Trace
0.10	0.50	0.10
0.10	1.00	0.15
0.10	2.00	0.28
0.10	4.00	0.40
0.10	12.00	0.50
0.33	0.33	0.33
0.33	3.00	0.43
1.00	0.33	0.59
1.00	6.00	0.68

^a Baker analysed reagent. ^b Xenon lamp with 350 nm out-off filter.

The data of Table 3 present evidence for photo-assisted decay of ammonia in the presence of either α-Fe₂O₃ or Cr₂O₃. Each line of data in Table 3 represents a separate experiment at the end of which the yield of NH₃ was determined. It is apparent that with either α-Fe₂O₃ or Cr₂O₃ as catalyst, there is a smaller net increase in the amount of NH₃ under illumination in the presence of N₂ in solutions initially dosed with ammonia than with pure water. Net decrease in the amount of NH₃ was observed under illumination when the amount of NH₃ initially added was 5 mol whether N₂ or Ar was passed.

TABLE 2—REDUCTION OF N₂ OVER Cr₂O₃^a AT 28° UNDER ILLUMINATION^b AT λ ≥ 420 nm IN PRESENCE OF BULK LIQUID WATER. EVIDENCE FOR LIMITING YIELDS OF NH₃.

Proportion of catalyst w/v%	Reaction gas	Reaction time h	Total yield of NH ₃ mol
0.10	N ₂	0.5	0.57
0.10	N ₂	1.0	0.94
0.10	N ₂	4.0	1.10
0.10	N ₂	19.0	0.89
0.10	Air	1.0	0.50
0.10	Air	3.0	1.10
0.10	Air	12.0	0.97
0.033	N ₂	19.0	0.56
0.33	N ₂	12.0	0.93
1.00	N ₂	10.0	1.24
0.033	Air	11.0	0.54
0.165	Air	12.0	1.1
0.33	Air	12.0	1.05

^a Fisher. ^b Xenon lamp with 420 nm cut-off filter.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF ADDED NH₃ ON YIELDS IN THE REDUCTION OF N₂ OVER α-Fe₂O₃^a and Cr₂O₃^b AT 27-28° UNDER ILLUMINATION^c AT λ ≥ 420 nm IN PRESENCE OF BULK LIQUID WATER. EVIDENCE FOR DECOMPOSITION OF NH₃.

Catalyst	Atmosphere ^d	Reaction period h	Initially added	Amount of NH ₃ after reaction mol	Difference
Fe ₂ O ₃	N ₂	3	none	0.87	+0.87
Fe ₂ O ₃	N ₂	1	0.10	0.21	+0.11
Fe ₂ O ₃	N ₂	7	2.0	2.4	+0.4
Fe ₂ O ₃	Ar	20	5.0	2.8	-2.2
Fe ₂ O ₃	Ar	22	5.1	3.3	-1.8
(Fe ₂ O ₃ dark)	Ar	20	5.0	4.6	-0.4
Cr ₂ O ₃	N ₂	3	none	0.93	+0.93
Cr ₂ O ₃	N ₂	22	none	0.93	+0.93
Cr ₂ O ₃	N ₂	7	0.30	0.98	+0.68
Cr ₂ O ₃	N ₂	24	5.0	3.7	-1.3
(Cr ₂ O ₃ dark)	N ₂	20	5.0	4.9	-0.1
Cr ₂ O ₃	Ar	24	5.1	3.1	-2.0
(Cr ₂ O ₃ dark)	Ar	20	5.2	4.9	-0.3

^a 0.10 w/v% Baker, A.R. ^b 0.17 w/v% Baker, A.R. ^c Xenon lamp with 420 nm cut-off filter. ^d 1 atm., 2-5 ml min⁻¹ flow-rate.

The decrease was about 60% larger with Ar than with N₂. The decrease under illumination with N₂ present or absent was several times larger than it was in the dark.

The data of Table 4 show little or no decay of the catalytic activity of α-Fe₂O₃ or Cr₂O₃ in, respectively, 44 or 38 h of use of their aqueous suspensions for reduction of N₂. Each line of data in Table 4 represents a separate experiment at the end of which the cell contents were centrifuged, the supernatant liquid removed and the yield of NH₃ determined. The recovered catalyst powder was then resuspended in an aliquot of pure water and passage of gas and illumination resumed. The whole reaction cycle was performed a total of five times after starting with fresh catalyst powder. With both pure N₂ over α-Fe₂O₃ and air over Cr₂O₃, the observed variation in the presumably limiting yield of NH₃ is relatively small and random.

TABLE 4—INFLUENCE OF RECYCLING α -Fe₂O₃^a AND Cr₂O₃^a ON YIELDS OF NH₃ IN THE REDUCTION OF N₂ AT 27-28° UNDER ILLUMINATION^b AT $\lambda \geq 420$ nm IN PRESENCE OF BULK LIQUID WATER: EVIDENCE FOR STABILITY OF CATALYTIC ACTION

Catalyst feedstock ^c	No. of times catal. reused	Period of illum.n. ^d h	Yield of NH ₃ mol
Fe ₂ O ₃ /N ₂	0	3	0.87
Fe ₂ O ₃ /N ₂	1	4	0.65
Fe ₂ O ₃ /N ₂	2	5	0.91
Fe ₂ O ₃ /N ₂	3	12	0.65
Fe ₂ O ₃ /N ₂	4	20	0.58
Cr ₂ O ₃ /air	0	12	0.97
Cr ₂ O ₃ /air	1	3	0.84
Cr ₂ O ₃ /air	2	15	0.86
Cr ₂ O ₃ /air	3	4	0.68
Cr ₂ O ₃ /air	4	4	0.85

^a 0.1 w/v % of Baker, A.R. catalyst. ^b Xenon lamp with 420 nm cut-off filter. ^c 30-40 ml min⁻¹ flow-rate of gas. ^d In individual experiments.

Yields of NH₃ using catalysts with widely differing band-gap energies are summarised in Table 5. Since neither the wt/vol proportion of catalyst, nor period of illumination, nor lower wavelength limit is constant over the set of experiments, comparison must be made with caution. (It must be noted that in no case has the assumption that the action of the metal oxides is only catalytic been proved.) To the extent that the data represents

TABLE 5—REDUCTION AT 30° OF N₂ BY AQUEOUS SUSPENSIONS OF ILLUMINATED PHOTOCATALYSTS: BAND-GAP SEQUENCE

Catalyst w/v %	Out-off ^a λ (nm)/period of illum.n. (h)	Band-gap energy ^c eV	Yield of NH ₃ mol
La-Ni-oxide/0.17	<u>420/16</u>	0	<u>0.32</u>
Platinised La-Ni-oxide/0.17	<u>420/36</u>	0	<u>1.7</u>
La-Ti-oxide/0.33	<u>320/24</u>	0	<u>2.9</u>
CoO/0.33	<u>320/15</u>	0.8	3.6
Co ₃ O ₄ /0.10	<u>420/12</u>	0.9	<u>1.7</u>
Pr ₆ O ₁₁ /0.10	<u>350/6</u>	1.2	<u>0.49</u>
TeO ₂ /0.10	<u>350/10</u>	1.5	0.97
Cr ₂ O ₃ /0.33	<u>420/12</u>	1.9	<u>0.96</u>
α -Fe ₂ O ₃ /0.10	<u>420/12</u>	2.2	<u>0.65</u>
Nd ₂ O ₃ /0.17	<u>420/14</u>	2.2	<u>1.1</u>
WO ₃ /0.17	<u>420/16</u>	2.8	<u>1.6</u>
MoO ₃ /0.17	<u>420/16</u>	2.9	<u>1.25</u>
PbO/0.10	<u>350/22</u>	3.2	<u>0.81</u>
Fe ^{III} in mol sieve ^b /0.10	<u>420/5</u>	-	<u>1.9</u>

^a Illumination by xenon lamp. ^b Linde 5A molecular sieve exchanged with 1% aqueous BAR FeCl₃ and dried at 300°, illumination by a quartz halogen lamp. ^c Ref. 20.

photostationary state compositions, only the variation in the lower wavelength limit is significant. Comparison of the nine yields obtained with illumination at $\lambda \geq 420$ nm (corresponding to photon energy ≤ 2.96 eV) which are underlined with solid lines in Table 5, reveals no consistent pattern of variation of plateau yields with band-gap energy.

Similarly, the three yields obtained with illumination at $\lambda \geq 350$ nm (3.55 eV) which are underlined with dotted lines, do not vary systematically with band-gap energy. The two yields obtained with $\lambda \geq 320$ nm (3.88 eV) are significantly higher than all the others but no conclusion can be drawn as to the reason for this observation. It is noteworthy that one of the catalysts, Fe^{III} in Linde molecular sieve 5A, is neither a semiconductor nor metallic. The significance of the effectiveness of catalysts with small band-gaps is taken up below at the end of next section, in connection with results obtained in the absence of bulk liquid water.

The formal activation energy for the formation of NH₃ in 0.1 wt/vol aqueous suspensions of α -Fe₂O₃ (Baker, A.R.) illuminated at $\lambda \geq 420$ nm with N₂ passing at 60 ml min⁻¹ was determined in the usual way. Reaction periods for individual runs were 20-48 h and reaction temperatures were 40, 50, 60 and 70°. Under these conditions, negligible amounts of NH₃ remain in the reaction cell; essentially the entire product is collected in the traps. Decay of NH₃ does not complicate the picture under these conditions. The resulting apparent activation energy, 46 kJ mol⁻¹, is relatively large. This experiment has practical significance. It demonstrates that not only can decay of NH₃ be avoided by raising the reaction temperature high enough to drive it from solution, but the rate of conversion of N₂ to NH₃ can be substantially increased by raising the temperature.

Reduction of N₂ in absence of bulk liquid water: The data of Table 6 show that N₂ is reduced to

TABLE 6—REDUCTION OF N₂^a BY WATER OVER α -Fe₂O₃^b AT 28° UNDER ILLUMINATION^c AT $\lambda \geq 350$ nm IN ABSENCE OF BULK LIQUID WATER: EVIDENCE FOR STABILITY OF CATALYTIC ACTION

Total reaction time h	Total NH ₃ yield mol	Differential rate of formation of NH ₃ mol h ⁻¹
6	0.38	0.064
24	1.13	0.042
31	1.53	0.057
44	1.97	0.034
54	2.78	0.081
70	3.18	0.025
103	4.57	0.042
123	6.34	0.089
144	6.91	0.027
169	7.77	0.034
197	8.59	0.029
225	9.44	0.030

^a Flowing at 30 ml min⁻¹. ^b Baker, A.R. deposited from isopropanol and conditioned by heating at 300° under flowing argon for 12 h. ^c Xenon lamp with cut-off filter.

NH₃ over illuminated α -Fe₂O₃ in the presence of water vapor and absence of bulk liquid water. Although there are a few unexplained substantial fluctuations in the rate of production of NH₃, no significant trend is apparent over the 225 h of exposure. The results of a similar experiment

using a film of Cr₂O₃ presented in Table 7, are similar except that the experiment was continued for 329 h; differential rates were approximately half those obtained with α-Fe₂O₃ and there was an induction period. These experiments confirm that the activity of these catalysts is encouragingly stable. Since ammonia is rapidly swept into the collecting traps, the behavior of these 'dry' systems is not complicated by its decay.

A set of experiments employing a film of α-Fe₂O₃ illuminated at λ ≥ 420 nm and 29° showed that the rate of formation of NH₃ increased by a factor of six as the flow-rate of N₂ increased from 2 to 100 ml min⁻¹. Further doubling of the flow-rate had a negligible effect on the rate. The formal activation energy for the formation of NH₃ over α-Fe₂O₃ under illumination at λ ≥ 420 nm in the absence of bulk liquid water was determined in the usual way. Temperature was varied from 30 to 70° and the flow-rate of N₂ was 60 ml min⁻¹. The data correspond to an apparent activation energy of 19 kJ mol⁻¹, less than half the value observed in the presence of bulk liquid water. The efficiency of conversion of incident photons from a xenon lamp equipped with a 420 nm cut-off filter into energy stored in NH₃ was determined for the reaction in the absence of bulk liquid water at 30° by assuming that the photoreaction is the reverse of the combustion of NH₃.

Integrated incident light energy was measured with a 'Sunstation'¹⁹. This measurement yielded

$$\text{Engineering efficiency} = \frac{\text{Calculated stored energy}}{\text{Incident light energy}} \times 100 = 10^{-4}\%$$

for an experiment which produced 0.05 mol h⁻¹ of NH₃ at a flow-rate of 50 ml min⁻¹.

The rate of formation of NH₃ observed under similar conditions using a film of Co₃O₄ (band-gap = 0.9 eV) which had been deposited from water (Table 7) was more than two times that obtained with α-Fe₂O₃ which had been deposited from isopropanol. The rate of formation of NH₃ over a film of Co₃O₄ which had been deposited from aqueous isopropanol was more than five times that obtained with the latter α-Fe₂O₃ film. These results are consistent with the observations summarised in Table 5 which show that several low-band-gap materials are effective catalysts in the presence of bulk liquid water. ΔE° for the six-electron redox reaction, 1/2 N₂(g) + 5/2 H₂O(l) ⇌ NH₄OH(aq) + 3/4 O₂(g), is -1.23 V²¹. Thus, if the catalytic mechanism explicitly involves electrons from conduction bands, the overall reduction of N₂ over semiconductors with band-gap energies substantially less than 1.23 V requires the promotion of more than one electron on the average per electron equivalent transferred in the reaction. Such behavior would be required of La-Ni-oxide, La-Ti-oxide, CoO and Co₃O₄. Elucidation of the chemical mechanism

TABLE 7—REDUCTION OF N₂^a BY WATER OVER Cr₂O₃^b AT 28° UNDER ILLUMINATION^c AT λ ≥ 420 nm IN ABSENCE OF BULK LIQUID WATER: EVIDENCE FOR STABILITY OF CATALYTIC ACTION

Total reaction time h	Total NH ₃ yield mol	Differential rate of formation of NH ₃ mol h ⁻¹
18	0.08	0.001
46	0.80	0.020
68	0.94	0.016
91	1.22	0.018
116	1.73	0.020
140	2.26	0.022
164	2.73	0.020
188	2.93	0.008
214	3.79	0.033
238	4.81	0.042
266	5.28	0.017
286	5.67	0.015
318	5.89	0.012
329	6.66	0.042

^a Flowing at 30 ml min⁻¹. ^b Fisher, deposited from isopropanol and conditioned by heating on flowing argon at 300° for 12 h. ^c Xenon lamp with 420 nm cut-off filter.

of such processes remains to be accomplished. Similarly, no mechanistic explanation of the catalytic effectiveness of zeolite 5A containing Fe^{III} can be offered at present.

Films of several catalysts which had been shown²² to be active in the photoassisted reduction of CO₂ by H₂ were found to also promote the reduction of N₂ by water vapour under illumination (λ ≥ 420 nm) at rates similar to that observed with α-Fe₂O₃. These catalysts included Co-Mo-Al-oxide, Co-Mo-Ti-oxide, Zn-Fe-oxide and platinised La-Ni-oxide. Activity was followed for periods ranging from 48 to 146 h.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by ARCO Solar, Inc.

References

- G. N. SCHRAUZER and T. D. GUTH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 7189.
- G. N. SCHRAUZER, T. D. GUTH, M. R. PALMER and J. SALEHI in "Solar Energy: Chemical Conversion and Storage", eds. R. R. HAUTALA, R. B. KING and C. KUTAL, Humana Press, Clifton, 1979, p. 261.
- H. MIYAMA, N. FUJII and Y. NAGAE, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1980, **74**, 523.
- G. N. SCHRAUZER, N. STRAMPACH, L. N. HUI, M. R. PALMER and J. SALEHI, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 1983, **80**, 3873.
- V. AUGUGLIARO, A. LAURICELLA, L. RIZZUTI, M. SCHIAVELLO and A. SCLAFANI in "Hydrogen Energy Press", Proceedings 8rd World Hydrogen Energy Conference, Tokyo, June 1980, eds. T. N. VEZIROGLU, K. FURKI and T. OHTA, pp. 2, 589.
- V. AUGUGLIARO, A. LAURICELLO, L. RIZZUTI, M. SCHIAVELLO and A. SCLAFANI, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 1982, **7**, 845.
- V. AUGUGLIARO, F. D'ALBA, L. RIZZUTI, M. SCHIAVELLO and A. SCLAFANI, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 1982, **7**, 861.

8. P. L. YUE, F. KHAN and L. RIZZUTI, *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, 1983, **38**, 1893.
9. H. VAN DAMME and W. HALL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 4373.
10. P. P. RADFORD and C. G. FRANCIS, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1983, 1520.
11. D. MONHEIT, S. GRAYER, N. GODINGER, V. KATZIR and M. HALMANN, "Abstracts of the 5th International Conference on Photochemical Conversion and Storage of Solar Energy", Osaka 1984, p. 75.
12. F. KAHN, P.-L. YUE, L. RIZZUTI, V. AUGUGLIARO and M. SCHIAVELLO, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1981, 1049.
13. F. KHAN, P. YUE, L. RIZZUTI, V. AUGUGLIARO and A. BRUCATO, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Prod. Res. Dev.*, 1983, **22**, 288.
14. N. N. LICHTIN, U. S. Pat., 4 427 509/1984.
15. N. N. LICHTIN and K. M. VIJAYAKUMAR, U. S. Pat., 4 427 510/1984.
16. N. N. LICHTIN and E. BERMAN, U. S. Pat., 4 443 911/1984.
17. N. N. LICHTIN and K. M. VIJAYAKUMAR, "Abstracts of the 163rd Meeting of the Electrochemical Society", May 8-13, 1983, p. 782.
18. N. N. LICHTIN, K. M. VIJAYAKUMAR and M. M. KHADER, "Extended Abstracts of the 1985 Meeting of the International Solar Energy Society", 1985, p. 493.
19. E. BERMAN and D. BIRAN, *Solar Energy*, 1978, **20**, 465.
20. O. V. KRYLOV, "Catalysis by Non-metals", Academic Press, New York, 1970.
21. Lange's Handbook of Chemistry, 12th ed., ed. J. A. DEAN, McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York, 1979, 9-1.
22. K. M. VIJAYAKUMAR and N. N. LICHTIN, *J. Catal.*, 1984, **90**, 173.